

Appendix C: Additional results

Appendix C.1: Evolving populations

From the results obtained with the `EVOLVING` models, we observe a consistent evolution of the spin magnitude distributions across the mass range. This evolution progresses from lower spins at lower masses to higher spins at higher masses. However, the higher-mass distribution of spin magnitudes is not as tightly constrained as that of lower masses.

With the `EVOLVING GAUSSIAN` model, two potential spin evolution scenarios emerge, as illustrated in Fig. 1. Either the spin distribution maintains a stable peak position while spreading out towards higher spin magnitudes, or the width of the Gaussian distribution remains relatively fixed while the position of the distribution shifts. In either case, the model indicates an evolution in spin magnitudes from $10M_{\odot}$ to $100M_{\odot}$.

Fig. 1: **Evolving Gaussian parameters:** Corner plot of the population parameters $\hat{\mu}_{\chi}$ and $\hat{\sigma}_{\chi}$ of the `EVOLVING GAUSSIAN` model, obtained from the population inference of 59 real GW events from the GWTC-3 catalog.

The two `EVOLVING` models incorporating a window function, namely the `BETA TO BETA` and `BETA TO GAUSSIAN` models, suggest the possibility of a transition from one spin magnitude distribution to another, which is preferred against the `EVOLVING GAUSSIAN` model. These models support either a rapid transition around $40 M_{\odot}$ or a smoother transition at higher masses ($60 M_{\odot}$), as depicted in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3. However, it seems that the rapid transition around $45M_{\odot}$ is slightly preferred.

The angular spin of the tilt angles, the CBC merger rate reconstruction, and the sources' frame mass reconstruction all align closely with each other, particularly with the non-evolving baseline analysis, as demonstrated in Fig. 4.

We performed an extra test, following Abbott et al. (2023), comparing the reconstructed distribution of the spin magnitudes aligned with the orbital angular momentum, $|s_z|$, as a function of detector chirp mass \mathcal{M}_c . Fig. 5 shows the reconstructed 50% and 90% credible upper bounds for the spin magnitude aligned with the orbital angular momentum. Upper bounds seem to evolve to more rapidly spinning BHs starting around $40 M_{\odot}$. While in Abbott et al. (2023) this trend is explained as due to a lower constraint on the spin for massive BHs, here we still obtain as a consequence of a spin-mass relation (this trend is not observed if we remove the spin-mass relation, see Sec. D).

Fig. 2: **Critical Mass transition-steepness:** Corner plot of the mass transition point m_t and the transition steepness δ_{m_t} population parameters, obtained from the population inference of 59 real GW events from the GWTC-3 catalog with the `EVOLVING` models with a window function.

Fig. 3: **Window function:** Reconstruction of the window function $W(m)$ as a function of the mass, obtained from the population inference of GWTC-3 data with the `EVOLVING` models. The colored contours correspond to the 90% C.L.

Appendix C.2: Mixture populations

In this section, we present further explanations of the results obtained with the `MIXTURE` models. In particular, when the second population is allowed to arrive down to $2 M_{\odot}$, the posterior distribution of the mixing parameter λ_{pop} exhibits a slight bimodality with the minimum mass of the second distribution ($m_{\text{min}}^{\text{pop}2}$). This bi-modality is presented in Fig. 6 and Fig. 7, and suggests that there is some support for a lower value of λ_{pop} , finding at the same time a minimum mass for the second population close to a few solar masses. This minimum mass corresponds to the one of the first population. Nonetheless, the mode given by $\lambda_{\text{pop}} \sim 0.98$ and $m_{\text{min}}^{\text{pop}2} \sim 35M_{\odot}$ is strongly preferred by the analysis, thus favoring the hypothesis that a subpopulation of BHs with different spins could begin around $40M_{\odot}$.

Fig. 4 shows the reconstructed mass spectrum obtained with the three `MIXTURE` models; the inferred spectra are in perfect agreement with the canonical reconstruction of the non-evolving analysis, as well as with the mass spectrum reconstructed by `EVOLVING` models. Similarly, the two CBC merger rates inferred by the `MIXTURE` model are all in agreement with each other and

Fig. 4: **Mass spectrum reconstruction:** Reconstructed mass spectra of the primary (left column) and secondary (right column) masses obtained from the population inference of 59 real GW events from the GWTC-3 catalog, with the MIXTURE VANILLA model (first row), MIXTURE PEAK (second row), MIXTURE PAIRED (third row), EVOLVING GAUSSIAN (fourth row), BETA TO GAUSSIAN (fifth row), BETA TO BETA (sixth row) and the canonical VANILLA model (seventh row). The dotted lines are the median values and the colored contours the 90% C.L. inferred.

resemble the one of the baseline analysis. From Fig. 8, we argue that the BBH merger rate as a function of the redshift inferred for the first and second populations probably has the same trend. In other words, if the two subpopulations correspond to different formation channels, then their time-delay distributions between BBH formation and merger should be similar.

In order to validate the results observed with the MIXTURE models, we ran the same population inference removing the spin distributions (masses and rate only). We find that the Bayes factor between the MIXTURE model without spin and the simple non-evolving model is close to 1; this result highlights that the spin magnitude distribution is the determinant factor to disentangle

Fig. 5: **Aligned spin magnitude evolution:** Scatter plot representing the evolution of the aligned component of the spin magnitude s_z with respect to the chirp mass M_c , obtained from the population inference of 59 real GW events from the GWTC-3 catalog, obtained using the EVOLVING GAUSSIAN (top), the BETA TO GAUSSIAN (middle) and BETA TO BETA (bottom) models.

Fig. 6: **Mixture parameter:** Histograms of the inferred posterior distribution of the mixture parameter λ_{pop} for three different flavors of the MIXTURE model analysis on 59 real GW events from the GWTC-3 catalog, namely the MIXTURE VANILLA (red), MIXTURE PEAK (light blue) and MIXTURE PAIRED (dark blue).

the two subpopulations. Moreover, when the spin of the population inference MIXTURE is removed, the mixing parameter λ_{pop} is

Fig. 7: **Mixture bi-modality:** Corner plot of the mixture parameter λ_{pop} and the minimum mass of the second population $m_{\text{min}}^{\text{pop2}}$ inferred with the MIXTURE vanilla and MIXTURE PAIRED model from the population inference of 59 real GW events from the GWTC-3 catalog. The contours are the 90% C.L. estimated.

less constrained and can be in agreement with 1, i.e. the presence of only one population.

Appendix D: Sanity checks

As mentioned in the paper, to test and validate our new parametric models, as well as the population inference robustness, we performed two distinct sanity check analyzes: a mock-data challenge (MDC) and a “blurred” spin-mass analysis on real GW events.

Appendix D.1: Mock Data Challenge

The aim of the MDC is to understand how the Bayes factors and the spin-mass models react to a population of BBHs that does not actually include any spin-mass relation. We simulated sets of ~ 50 detected GW events, in which we know that there is no spin-mass correlation. These events were drawn from the injection set used to estimate the selection effects in the main analysis, so they are representative of the sensitivity reached for GWTC-3. Here, we assume that we perfectly measure population parameters of the spins, masses, and distances in order to maximize the precision on the population parameters inferred by the different models.

GW events are simulated following an MD-like BBH merger rate, a mass distribution following a POWER LAW + PEAK vanilla model, and a spin distribution preferring lowly spinning BBHs nearly aligned with the orbital angular momentum. The distributions of masses and spins are indicated with a black dashed line in the figures referenced below.

We report a summary of the results in the form of Bayes factors in the upper half of Tab. 1.

From the Bayes factor obtained for the MDC analysis, it is clear that the canonical non-evolving model is always preferred against the MIXTURE and EVOLVING GAUSSIAN models and equally preferred for the BETA TO BETA and BETA TO GAUSSIAN models.

Fig. 8: **CBC merger rate:** Histograms of the inferred posterior distribution of the CBC merger rate parameter γ , estimated for four distinct analysis on 59 real GW events from the GWTC-3 catalog. Top: Vanilla analysis with a mono population model. Middle: Posterior of γ for the first population of the MIXTURE analysis. Bottom: Posterior of γ for the second population of the MIXTURE analysis.

This result demonstrates that the spin-mass correlation directly drives the model selection in the main analysis presented with the real set of GW data in the article.

Appendix D.1.1: Considerations on Evolving models

Fig. 9 and Fig. 10 are the reconstructed spin magnitudes and tilt angles obtained from the models MIXTURE and EVOLVING. For the MIXTURE model, the results show strong agreement with the original data, accurately capturing the true spin distributions. Similarly, the EVOLVING model also yields excellent results, correctly identifying the spin magnitudes of the injected population. The deviations in the posterior predictive checks above $70 M_{\odot}$ are due to the prior ranges on m_t and δm_t governing the window function. Specifically, since no transition mass is present for the spin population, m_t is not bounded within the upper limit of its prior range ($100 M_{\odot}$). As a consequence, the posterior predictive check of the window function, see Fig. 11, still has some support for a transition happening below $100 M_{\odot}$.

In analogy to the real analysis, we also replicate the plot on the $|s_z|$ detector chirp mass relation. Fig. 12 shows us that when

Table 1: Population model selection (MDC and Blurred)

Mock Data Challenge

Model	$\log_{10} \mathcal{B}$	$\log_{10} \mathcal{L}_{\max}$
MIXTURE VANILLA	-1.36	2.53
MIXTURE PEAK	-3.69	-0.88
MIXTURE PAIRED	-3.26	3.16
EVOLVING GAUSSIAN	-6.07	-1.46
BETA TO GAUSSIAN	-0.61	1.86
BETA TO BETA	-0.21	0.43

Spin-mass blurred analysis

Model	$\log_{10} \mathcal{B}$	$\log_{10} \mathcal{L}_{\max}$
MIXTURE VANILLA	0.90	0.92
MIXTURE PEAK	0.76	0.40
MIXTURE PAIRED	-1.11	-2.24
EVOLVING GAUSSIAN	-3.34	-0.23
BETA TO GAUSSIAN	-0.28	0.18
BETA TO BETA	0.06	0.40

Notes. Base 10 logarithm Bayes factors (second column) and the maximum of log-likelihood ratio (third column) obtained for each of our six models, compared to the canonical non evolving model when inferring the population parameters of the mock data challenge (MDC) and the blurred analysis.

Fig. 9: Spin population spectra (MDC): Reconstructed spectra of the spin magnitude χ (left) and the cosine of the tilt angle (right), obtained from the population inference of simulated GW data with no spin-mass evolution (MDC) using the MIXTURE models. The plain lines are the median of the reconstructed spectra and the colored contours are the 90% C.L. And the dotted black line is the true distribution in the data.

no spin-mass relation is present, and GWs masses and spins are well-measured, no evolving trend is observed between these two variables.

Concerning the EVOLVING GAUSSIAN model, Fig. 13 shows the inferred distribution for the population parameters driving evo-

Fig. 10: Evolving spin magnitude spectra (MDC): Joy plot of the reconstructed spin magnitude spectra obtained with the EVOLVING GAUSSIAN (left) and EVOLVING window (middle and right) models on simulated GW data (MDC). The black line is the true distribution in the data. The colored contours are the reconstructed spectra defined as the 90% C.L. The discrepancies in the higher mass regime are induced by the prior effects since the inferred transition mass parameter posterior m_t is railing on its prior range. This effect is not to worry in the main analysis since the posterior nicely converges in its prior range.

Fig. 11: **Window function (MDC and blurred)**: Reconstructed window function for the MDC (top) and the blurred (bottom) sanity checks, with the BETA TO GAUSSIAN and BETA TO BETA. The colored contours are the 90% C.L. inferred spectra.

Fig. 12: **Aligned spin magnitude evolution MDC**: Scatter plot representing the evolution of the aligned component of the spin magnitude s_z with respect to the chirp mass \mathcal{M}_c , obtained from the population inference of simulated GW data (MDC) using the EVOLVING GAUSSIAN (top), the BETA TO GAUSSIAN (middle) and BETA TO BETA (bottom) models.

lution of the spin mean and width. We can observe that, contrary to the real analysis, the model correctly supports no evolution of the spin magnitude with the mass.

Appendix D.1.2: Considerations on mixing models

For MIXTURE models, in Figs. 14-15, we studied the response of λ_{pop} and its interplay with the minimum mass of the secondary subpopulation. For the MIXTURE VANILLA and MIXTURE PAIRED analysis, the inference is not able to distinguish the presence of the two populations as the posteriors on the mixture fraction are informative. The minimum mass of the secondary population also strongly supports a value corresponding to the overall minimum of the true population. For the MIXTURE PEAK MODEL, the mixture fraction is constrained as the gaussian peak is used to fit the central peak of the POWER LAW + PEAK distribution that has been simulated. This can be clearly seen in Fig. 16 where we report the mass posterior predictive checks from the models in overlap with the simulated distribution. The posteriors on the

Fig. 13: **Evolving Gaussian parameter MDC:** Corner plot of the population parameters governing the evolution of the mean and width of the Gaussian distribution modeling the spin magnitude in the EVOLVING GAUSSIAN model, namely $\dot{\mu}_\chi$ and $\dot{\sigma}_\chi$.

Fig. 15: **Mixture-mass relation:** Overlapped corner plots of the mixing parameter λ_{pop} and the minimum mass of the secondary population $m_{\text{min}}^{\text{pop}2}$, obtained from the MIXTURE VANILLA and MIXTURE PAIRED models from the MDC and the blurred analysis.

Fig. 14: **Mixing parameter (MDC and blurred):** (Top plot) posteriors distribution of the inferred λ_{pop} from the MDC analysis using the three flavors of the MIXTURE model. (Bottom plot) posteriors distribution of the inferred λ_{pop} from the blurred analysis using the three flavors of the MIXTURE model.

CBC merger rate parameter γ are shown in Fig. 17 and are all consistent with the injected value of 2.7.

Appendix D.2: Spin-mass blurred analysis with real data

Another sanity check that we perform is to repeat all of our analyses on a spin-mass blinded data set. We select the same GW events as the ones considered for the real analysis, but this time we permute among them their inferred spin values. In the limit that the determination of the other GW parameters, and the selection biases, are not strongly related to the spin magnitudes, this procedure artificially blinds the dataset to any spin-mass relation.

We warrant that in the low number detections’ regime, if there is really a spin-mass relation, shuffling the inferred spin values might not 100% blind the data from the spin-mass relation. The motivation is that low-mass events are more numerous, therefore there is an higher probability that the spin of a low-mass event will be reassigned to a low-mass event thus preserving the spin-mass correlation. However, the shuffling of the spin values is expected for sure to blind any spin-mass relation at high masses (since the events are less numerous). We refer to this type of analysis as spin-mass “blurred” analysis to indicate that we are not able to 100% generate blinded data. The spin-mass values used for this analysis are displayed in Fig. 18 for the blurred spin-mass estimations.

The Bayes factors and log-likelihood ratios obtained from the blinded analyses are reported in Tab. 1. All the models report inconclusive results, having no preference for any of the evolving spin-mass models. In terms of population constraints for the different models, we find very similar results as the ones described for the MDC.

Appendix D.2.1: Considerations on Evolving models

Fig. 19 shows the posterior predictive check for the three EVOLVING models. In comparison with the real analysis, we still observe that at low masses the analysis reconstructs a spin distribution preferring low spin values, but the reconstruction becomes more

Fig. 16: **Mass spectrum reconstruction MDC:** Reconstructed mass spectra of the primary (left column) and secondary (right column) masses obtained from MDC population inference of the MDC with the MIXTURE VANILLA model (first row), MIXTURE PEAK (second row), MIXTURE PAIRED (third row), EVOLVING GAUSSIAN (fourth row), BETA TO GAUSSIAN (fifth row), BETA TO BETA (sixth row) and the canonical VANILLA model (seventh row). The dotted lines are the median values and the colored contours the 90% C.L. inferred.

and more uncertain as the mass value increases. This is to the fact that as low-mass events are more numerous, the spin shuffling does not effectively blind the data to a spin-mass relation. However, the spin-mass relation is diluted enough for the Bayes factors on model selection to become inconclusive.

Concerning the BETA TO GAUSSIAN and BETA TO BETA model, Fig. 11 (bottom panel) and Fig. 20 show the posterior predic-

Fig. 17: **CBC merger rate (MDC and blurred):** Inferred posterior of the γ parameter from the CBC merger rate population model. Left plot: Estimated γ from the MDC with the non evolving canonical model (top), first population with MIXTURE models (middle) and second population with the MIXTURE models (bottom). Right plot: Estimated γ from the blurred analysis with the non evolving canonical model (top), first population with MIXTURE models (middle) and second population with the MIXTURE models (bottom)

tive checks and population posteriors on the window function. For the real analysis, we observe that the window function supports a transition at higher masses, which is a hint of the fact that the spin shuffling procedure has partially hidden the spin-mass relation in real data. Also for this test case, in Fig. 21 we study the trend between $|s_z|$ and the detector chirp mass, finding no evident evolution as the one observed in the real analysis.

Regarding the EVOLVING GAUSSIAN model, we find that there is no support for a continuous evolution of the distribution of the spin magnitude. Fig. 22 shows the posterior on parameters governing the evolution of the mean and standard deviation of the Gaussian spin distribution.

Appendix D.2.2: Considerations on the mixture models

Fig. 23 shows the posterior predictive checks for the spin magnitudes and tilt angle distributions. In this case, both subpopulations support low spin values with the secondary population (more massive events) slightly more uncertain. Similar to the MDC test, the mixing parameter λ_{pop} shown in Fig. 14 and Fig. 15 is not able to pinpoint the presence of any subpopulation as opposed to what we observed with unblinded GW data.

Fig. 18: **Blurred Mass-Spin dataset:** Scatter plot of the GW events used in the analysis. They correspond to the 59 binary black hole events from the GWTC-3 catalog selected with an IFAR ≥ 1 yr. The x-axis shows the source frame masses m^s and the y-axis displays the dimensionless spin magnitudes χ . The errors bars are the 1σ uncertainties of the official LVK parameter estimation samples for each GW event.

Fig. 20: **Spin-mass transition (MDC and blurred):** Overlapped corner plots of the population parameters governing the spin transition as a function of the mass, namely m_t and δm_t ; for the two SHIFTING models in the case of the MDC and the blurred analysis.

Fig. 19: **Mixture spin magnitude spectra (blurred):** Joy plot of the reconstructed spin magnitude spectra obtained with the EVOLVING GAUSSIAN (left) and EVOLVING window models (middle and right) on 59 real GW events from the GWTC-3 catalog, shuffled to remove the spin-mass correlation (blurred). The colored contours are the 90% C.L. reconstructed spectra from the population inference.

The mass spectrum reconstructed in this test still agrees with the one reconstructed in the real analysis thus indicating that the spin-mass relation is not an artifact created by the fit of the mass spectrum. Fig. 24 presents the reconstructed mass spectrum for both model families, showing good agreement among spectra and with the non-evolving analysis. This agreement extends to

the inferred compact binary coalescence (CBC) merger rate, as depicted in Fig. 17.

In conclusion, when analyzing real GW data without spin-mass correlation, the MIXTURE and EVOLVING models successfully reconstruct the correct mass, merger rate and spin spectra, while indicating no support for spin evolution. Furthermore, these models are disfavored by the Bayes factors.

Fig. 21: **Aligned spin magnitude evolution blurred**: Scatter plot representing the evolution of the aligned component of the spin magnitude s_z with respect to the chirp mass M_c , obtained from the population inference of real but shuffled GW data (swap) using the EVOLVING GAUSSIAN (top), the BETA TO GAUSSIAN (middle) and BETA TO BETA (bottom) models.

Fig. 22: **Evolving Gaussian parameter blurred**: Corner plot of the population parameters governing the evolution of the mean and width of the Gaussian distribution modeling the sp in magnitude in the EVOLVING GAUSSIAN model, namely $\dot{\mu}_\chi$ and $\dot{\sigma}_\chi$.

Fig. 23: **Spin population spectra (blurred)**: Reconstructed spectra of the spin magnitude χ (left) and the cosine of the tilt angle (right), obtained from the population inference of 59 real GW events from the GWTC-3 catalog which as been shuffled to remove any spin-mass correlation (blurred). The plain lines are the median of the reconstructed spectra and the colored contours are the 90% C.L. And the dotted black line is the true distribution in the data.

Fig. 24: **Mass spectrum reconstruction blurred:** Reconstructed mass spectra of the primary (left column) and secondary (right column) masses obtained from blurred population inference of the MDC with the MIXTURE VANILLA model (first row), MIXTURE PEAK (second row), MIXTURE PAIRED (third row), EVOLVING GAUSSIAN (fourth row), BETA TO GAUSSIAN (fifth row), BETA TO BETA (sixth row) and the canonical VANILLA model (seventh row). The dotted lines are the median values and the colored contours the 90% C.L. inferred.

Appendix E: Prior ranges for population inference

Appendix E.1: Vanilla analysis prior ranges

Table 2: Prior ranges and population parameters for the non evolving Vanilla analysis, construct with a Power Law plus Peak for the masses, a Default spin model and a MD CBC merger rate.

Parameter	Description	Prior
Masses: Power Law plus Peak		
α	Spectral index for the PL of the primary mass distribution.	$\mathcal{U}(0, 8)$
β	Spectral index for the PL of the mass ratio distribution.	$\mathcal{U}(-1, 10)$
m_{\min}	Minimum mass of the primary mass distribution [M_{\odot}].	$\mathcal{U}(1M_{\odot}, 8M_{\odot})$
m_{\max}	Maximum mass of the primary mass distribution [M_{\odot}].	$\mathcal{U}(70M_{\odot}, 130M_{\odot})$
λ_g	Fraction of the model in the Gaussian component.	$\mathcal{U}(0, 1)$
μ_g	Mean of the Gaussian in the primary mass distribution [M_{\odot}].	$\mathcal{U}(20M_{\odot}, 50M_{\odot})$
σ_g	Width of the Gaussian in the primary mass distribution [M_{\odot}].	$\mathcal{U}(1M_{\odot}, 10M_{\odot})$
δ_m	Range of mass tapering at the lower end of the mass distribution [M_{\odot}].	$\mathcal{U}(1M_{\odot}, 10M_{\odot})$
Spins: Default model		
$\alpha_{\chi}^{\text{pop1}}$	First parameter of the Beta distribution for the spin magnitude.	$\mathcal{U}(1, 10)$
$\beta_{\chi}^{\text{pop1}}$	Second parameter of the Beta distribution for the spin magnitude.	$\mathcal{U}(1, 10)$
σ_t^{pop1}	Standard deviation of the truncated gaussian for the cosine tilt angle distribution.	$\mathcal{U}(0, 5)$
ξ^{pop1}	Mixing parameter for the cosine of the tilt angle distribution.	$\mathcal{U}(0, 1)$
Rate: MD		
γ	Slope of the power law regime before the point z_p .	$\mathcal{U}(0, 8)$
k	Slope of the power law regime after the point z_p .	$\mathcal{U}(0, 8)$
z_p	Redshift turning point between the power law regimes .	$\mathcal{U}(0, 8)$
\mathcal{R}_0	Local value of the CBC merger rate, at $z = 0$.	$\mathcal{U}(0, 100)$

Appendix E.2: Mass prior ranges

Table 3: Prior ranges and population parameters used for the MIXTURE vanilla and paired models.

Parameter	Description	Prior
Pop1: Power Law plus Peak		
α^{pop1}	Spectral index for the PL of the primary mass distribution.	$\mathcal{U}(0, 8)$
β^{pop1}	Spectral index for the PL of the mass ratio distribution.	$\mathcal{U}(-1, 8)$
$m_{\text{min}}^{\text{pop1}}$	Minimum mass of the primary mass distribution [M_{\odot}].	$\mathcal{U}(1M_{\odot}, 8M_{\odot})$
$m_{\text{max}}^{\text{pop1}}$	Maximum mass of the primary mass distribution [M_{\odot}].	$\mathcal{U}(45M_{\odot}, 60M_{\odot})$
$\lambda_{\text{g}}^{\text{pop1}}$	Fraction of the model in the Gaussian component.	$\mathcal{U}(0, 1)$
$\mu_{\text{g}}^{\text{pop1}}$	Mean of the Gaussian in the primary mass distribution [M_{\odot}].	$\mathcal{U}(20M_{\odot}, 50M_{\odot})$
$\sigma_{\text{g}}^{\text{pop1}}$	Width of the Gaussian in the primary mass distribution [M_{\odot}].	$\mathcal{U}(1M_{\odot}, 10M_{\odot})$
δ_m^{pop1}	Range of mass tapering at the lower end of the mass distribution [M_{\odot}].	$\mathcal{U}(1M_{\odot}, 10M_{\odot})$
Pop2: Power Law		
α^{pop2}	Spectral index for the PL of the primary mass distribution.	$\mathcal{U}(0, 8)$
β^{pop2}	Spectral index for the PL of the mass ratio distribution.	$\mathcal{U}(-1, 8)$
$m_{\text{min}}^{\text{pop2}}$	Minimum mass of the primary mass distribution [M_{\odot}].	$\mathcal{U}(1M_{\odot}, 8M_{\odot})$
$m_{\text{max}}^{\text{pop2}}$	Maximum mass of the primary mass distribution [M_{\odot}].	$\mathcal{U}(80M_{\odot}, 130M_{\odot})$
δ_m^{pop2}	Range of mass tapering at the lower end of the mass distribution [M_{\odot}].	$\mathcal{U}(1M_{\odot}, 10M_{\odot})$
Common parameters		
λ_{pop}	Fraction of the population pop1 w.r.t to the overall population.	$\mathcal{U}(0,1)$

Table 4: Prior ranges and population parameters used for the MIXTURE PEAK models.

Parameter	Description	Prior
Pop1: Power Law plus Peak		
α^{pop1}	Spectral index for the PL of the primary mass distribution.	$\mathcal{U}(0, 8)$
β^{pop1}	Spectral index for the PL of the mass ratio distribution.	$\mathcal{U}(-1, 8)$
$m_{\text{min}}^{\text{pop1}}$	Minimum mass of the primary mass distribution [M_{\odot}].	$\mathcal{U}(1M_{\odot}, 8M_{\odot})$
$m_{\text{max}}^{\text{pop1}}$	Maximum mass of the primary mass distribution [M_{\odot}].	$\mathcal{U}(80M_{\odot}, 130M_{\odot})$
δ_m^{pop1}	Range of mass tapering at the lower end of the mass distribution [M_{\odot}].	$\mathcal{U}(1M_{\odot}, 10M_{\odot})$
Pop2: Power Law		
μ^{pop2}	Mean of the gaussian	$\mathcal{U}(20M_{\odot}, 50M_{\odot})$
σ^{pop2}	Standard deviation of the gaussian	$\mathcal{U}(2M_{\odot}, 10M_{\odot})$
Common parameters		
λ_{pop}	Fraction of the population pop1 w.r.t to the overall population.	$\mathcal{U}(0, 1)$

Table 5: Prior ranges and mass populations parameters used for the three EVOLVING models.

Parameter	Description	Prior
Power Law plus Peak		
α	Spectral index for the PL of the primary mass distribution.	$\mathcal{U}(0, 8)$
β	Spectral index for the PL of the mass ratio distribution.	$\mathcal{U}(-1, 10)$
m_{min}	Minimum mass of the primary mass distribution [M_{\odot}].	$\mathcal{U}(1M_{\odot}, 8M_{\odot})$
m_{max}	Maximum mass of the primary mass distribution [M_{\odot}].	$\mathcal{U}(70M_{\odot}, 130M_{\odot})$
λ_g	Fraction of the model in the Gaussian component.	$\mathcal{U}(0, 1)$
μ_g	Mean of the Gaussian in the primary mass distribution [M_{\odot}].	$\mathcal{U}(20M_{\odot}, 50M_{\odot})$
σ_g	Width of the Gaussian in the primary mass distribution [M_{\odot}].	$\mathcal{U}(1M_{\odot}, 10M_{\odot})$
δ_m	Range of mass tapering at the lower end of the mass distribution [M_{\odot}].	$\mathcal{U}(1M_{\odot}, 10M_{\odot})$

Appendix E.3: CBC merger rate prior ranges

Table 6: Prior ranges and CBC merger rate population parameters used for the three flavors of the MIXTURE models.

Parameter	Description	Prior
Pop1: Madau&Dickinson rate		
γ^{pop1}	Slope of the power law regime before the point z_p .	$\mathcal{U}(0, 8)$
k^{pop1}	Slope of the power law regime after the point z_p .	$\mathcal{U}(0, 8)$
z_p^{pop1}	Redshift turning point between the power law regimes .	$\mathcal{U}(0, 8)$
Pop2: Madau&Dickinson rate		
γ^{pop2}	Slope of the power law regime before the point z_p .	$\mathcal{U}(0, 8)$
k^{pop2}	Slope of the power law regime after the point z_p .	$\mathcal{U}(0, 8)$
z_p^{pop2}	Redshift turning point between the power law regimes.	$\mathcal{U}(0, 8)$
Common parameters		
\mathcal{R}_0	Local value of the CBC merger rate, at $z = 0$.	$\mathcal{U}(0,100)$

Table 7: Prior ranges and CBC merger rate population parameters used for the three flavors of EVOLVING models.

Parameter	Description	Prior
Madau&Dickinson rate		
γ	Slope of the power law regime before the point z_p .	$\mathcal{U}(0, 8)$
k	Slope of the power law regime after the point z_p .	$\mathcal{U}(0, 8)$
z_p	Redshift turning point between the power law regimes .	$\mathcal{U}(0, 8)$
\mathcal{R}_0	Local value of the CBC merger rate, at $z = 0$.	$\mathcal{U}(0,100)$

Appendix E.4: Spin prior ranges

Table 8: Prior ranges and spin population parameters for the three flavors of the MIXTURE models.

Parameter	Description	Prior
Pop1: Default spin		
$\alpha_\chi^{\text{pop1}}$	First parameter of the Beta distribution for the spin magnitude.	$\mathcal{U}(1, 10)$
β_χ^{pop1}	Second parameter of the Beta distribution for the spin magnitude.	$\mathcal{U}(1, 10)$
σ_t^{pop1}	Standard deviation of the truncated gaussian for the cosine tilt angle distribution.	$\mathcal{U}(0, 5)$
ξ^{pop1}	Mixing parameter for the cosine of the tilt angle distribution.	$\mathcal{U}(0, 1)$
Pop2: Default spin		
$\alpha_\chi^{\text{pop2}}$	First parameter of the Beta distribution for the spin magnitude.	$\mathcal{U}(1, 10)$
β_χ^{pop2}	Second parameter of the Beta distribution for the spin magnitude.	$\mathcal{U}(1, 10)$
σ_t^{pop2}	Standard deviation of the truncated gaussian for the cosine tilt angle distribution.	$\mathcal{U}(0, 5)$
ξ^{pop2}	Mixing parameter for the cosine of the tilt angle distribution.	$\mathcal{U}(0, 1)$

Table 9: Prior ranges and spin population parameters for the EVOLVING model.

Parameter	Description	Prior
Evolving Gaussian		
μ_χ	Zero order parameter expansion of the mean of the gaussian for the spin magnitude	$\mathcal{U}(0, 1)$
σ_χ	Zero order parameter expansion of the standard deviation of the gaussian for the spin magnitude	$\mathcal{U}(10^{-3}, 2)$
$\dot{\mu}_\chi$	First order parameter expansion of the mean of the gaussian for the spin magnitude.	$\mathcal{U}(0, 0.1)$
$\dot{\sigma}_\chi$	First order parameter expansion of the standard deviation of the gaussian for the spin magnitude.	$\mathcal{U}(-0.1, 0.1)$
σ_t	Standard deviation of the truncated gaussian for the cosine tilt angle distribution.	$\mathcal{U}(0, 5)$
ξ	Mixing parameter for the cosine of the tilt angle distribution.	$\mathcal{U}(0, 1)$

Table 10: Prior ranges and spin population parameters for the EVOLVING Beta to Gaussian model.

Parameter	Description	Prior
Shifting Beta to Gaussian		
α_χ	First parameter of the Beta distribution for the spin magnitude.	$\mathcal{U}(1, 10)$
β_χ	Second parameter of the Beta distribution for the spin magnitude.	$\mathcal{U}(1, 10)$
μ_χ	Mean of the gaussian for the spin magnitude.	$\mathcal{U}(0, 1)$
σ_χ	Standard deviation of the gaussian for the spin magnitude.	$\mathcal{U}(10^{-3}, 2)$
σ_t	Standard deviation of the truncated gaussian for the cosine tilt angle distribution.	$\mathcal{U}(0, 5)$
ξ	Mixing parameter for the cosine of the tilt angle distribution.	$\mathcal{U}(0, 1)$
m_t	Critical mass at which the window function is equal to 0.5 (transition point).	$\mathcal{U}(10M_\odot, 100M_\odot)$
δ_{m_t}	Steepness of the window function.	$\mathcal{U}(1, 20)$
f_{mix}	Starting value of the window function.	$\mathcal{U}(0, 1)$

Table 11: Prior ranges and spin population parameters for the EVOLVING Beta to Beta model.

Parameter	Description	Prior
Shifting Beta to Gaussian		
$\alpha_{\chi}^{\text{low}}$	First parameter of the Beta distribution for the spin magnitude.	$\mathcal{U}(1, 10)$
$\beta_{\chi}^{\text{low}}$	Second parameter of the Beta distribution for the spin magnitude.	$\mathcal{U}(1, 10)$
$\alpha_{\chi}^{\text{high}}$	First parameter of the Beta distribution for the spin magnitude.	$\mathcal{U}(1, 10)$
$\beta_{\chi}^{\text{high}}$	Second parameter of the Beta distribution for the spin magnitude.	$\mathcal{U}(1, 10)$
σ_t	Standard deviation of the truncated gaussian for the cosine tilt angle distribution.	$\mathcal{U}(0, 5)$
ξ	Mixing parameter for the cosine of the tilt angle distribution.	$\mathcal{U}(0, 1)$
m_t	Critical mass at which the window function is equal to 0.5 (transition point).	$\mathcal{U}(10M_{\odot}, 100M_{\odot})$
δ_{m_t}	Steepness of the window function.	$\mathcal{U}(1, 20)$
f_{mix}	Starting value of the window function.	$\mathcal{U}(0, 1)$

References

Abbott, R. et al. 2023, Phys. Rev. X, 13, 011048